

A Short Communication for Women Faculty Members to Ensure the Code of Conduct to Uphold Professional Ethics in HEIs of Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

The Tamil Nadu State Council for Higher Education (TANSCHÉ) has introduced a Draft Model Policy on Code of Conduct for Teachers in the year 2025 to establish a structured framework for professionalism, ethical behaviour and academic excellence in higher educational institutions. This short communication for women evinces the key components of the policy, professional responsibilities, ethical conduct, teacher-student relationships, institutional duties and lifelong learning. By adhering to the guidelines, educators can foster an inclusive and innovative academic environment. This policy is applicable for both male and female faculty members. The policy highlights the essential role of teachers in shaping future generations while maintaining the dignity of the profession.

Keywords: Code of Conduct, Teachers, Professional Ethics, Higher Education, TANSCHÉ.

Introduction

Teachers play a transformative role in shaping the intellectual and ethical foundation of a society. By recognising this, the Tamil Nadu State Council for Higher Education (TANSCHÉ) has formulated a Draft Model Policy on Code of Conduct for Teachers to standardise professional behaviour and promote excellence in higher education. This policy serves as a benchmark for the educators to uphold integrity, inclusivity and innovation in teaching and mentoring roles. Women at higher educational institutions (HEIs) ought to master such code of ethics to shape up their career.

Professional Responsibilities

In the case of professional responsibilities, the policy emphasises academic excellence as a foundation of teaching. The teachers are expected to deliver quality education through effective pedagogy and continuous professional development (TANSCHÉ, 2025, p. 7). They have some of the key responsibilities to follow. They include Professional Responsibility, Assessment and Evaluation Research and Innovation, Ethical Conduct, Integrity, Professional Boundary, Harassment and Discrimination, Teacher-Student Relationship, Mentorship, Confidentiality, Institutional Responsibilities, Policy Compliance, Resource Utilisation and Lifelong Learning and Development. A faculty member has to ensure these areas of ethics are involved in the teaching career. They are explained below.

Assessment and Evaluation: A teaching faculty has to conduct fair and transparent evaluations to gauge student learning while teaching. (TANSCHÉ, 2025, pp. 7-8)

Research and Innovation: A teaching faculty has to uphold ethical standards in research, avoiding plagiarism in teaching and research. (TANSCHÉ, 2025, p. 8)

Ethical Conduct

A teaching faculty has to ensure that ethical behaviour is paramount in maintaining the dignity of the teaching profession. The policy mandates:

Integrity: A teaching faculty has to demonstrate honesty in all professional activities. (TANSCHÉ, 2025, p. 8)

Professional Boundaries: A teaching faculty has to avoid exploitation or favouritism in interactions with students and colleagues. (TANSCHÉ, 2025, p. 8)

Harassment and Discrimination: A teaching faculty has to ensure a discrimination-free environment by refraining from any form of bias based on caste, religion, or gender. (TANSCHÉ, 2025, p. 9)

Teacher-Student Relationship

A teaching faculty has to keep a positive relationship with the students. A respectful and equitable relationship between teachers and students is vital to develop the student's life and career. The policy highlights:

Mentorship: A teaching faculty has to guide students to achieve their potential while respecting individual differences. (TANSCHÉ, 2025, p. 9)

Confidentiality: A teaching faculty has to safeguard student privacy and academic records. (TANSCHÉ, 2025, p. 9)

Institutional Responsibilities

Teachers should uphold institutional responsibilities to cater to the development of the institution and thereby develop society. A teaching faculty has to align actions with the institutional goals. They should ensure:

Policy Compliance: A teaching faculty should adhere to university rules and contribute to institutional improvement. (TANSCHÉ, 2025, p. 9)

Resource Utilisation: A teaching faculty has to avoid the misuse of institutional resources for personal gains. (TANSCHÉ, 2025, p. 9)

Lifelong Learning and Development

The policy encourages teachers to engage in continuous professional growth through the conducting of workshops, conferences and research to develop the students' academic goals. (TANSCHÉ, 2025, p. 11) So, the institutions are tasked with facilitating these opportunities to enhance faculty capabilities.

Conclusion

The draft model policy on Code of Conduct for Teachers developed by TANSCHÉ provides a comprehensive framework to elevate the ideals of the teaching profession. By adhering to these codes, women educators can develop an environment of respect, innovation and excellence that ultimately benefits the students, the institution and the society. The policy's emphasis on ethical conduct, professional responsibilities and lifelong learning draws attention to the transformative power of education in the 21st Century.

References

[1] Tamil Nadu State Council for Higher Education (TANSCHÉ). (2025). *Draft Model Policy on Code of Conduct for Teachers*. Retrieved from TANSCHÉ Official Document.

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